

Pyramidellidae (Gastropoda, Heterobranchia) from the EMEPC/PEPC/Luso/2012 oceanographic expedition to Josephine Seamount in the Northern Atlantic

Pyramidellidae (Gastropoda, Heterobranchiala) de la expedición oceanográfica EMEPC/PEPC/Luso/2012 al monte submarino Josephine en el Atlántico norte

Anselmo PEÑAS*, Emilio ROLÁN** & Frank SWINNEN***

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ABSTRACT

In the present work the species of the family Pyramidellidae collected by the EMEPC/PEPC/Luso/2012 Expedition to the submarine Atlantic Bank "Josephine Seamount" located between Madeira and mainland Portugal, are revised. A total of 16 species were found, 9 of which were previously known, while 7 are new for science: among the latter, 1 belongs to the genus *Pyrgulina*, 4 to the genus *Odostomia*, and 2 to the genus *Eulimella*. *Chrysallida stefanisi* (Jeffreys, 1869) is transferred to *Pyrgulina* and compared to the new species. Furthermore, 9 species are new records from the Josephine Seamount (1 *Parthenina*, 2 *Odostomia*, 1 *Ondina*, 1 *Eulimella* and 4 *Turbonilla*).

RESUMEN

Se revisan las especies de la familia Pyramidellidae que fueron recolectadas en la expedición EMEPC/PEPC/Luso/2012 al banco atlántico submarino "Josephine Seamount" situado entre Madeira y Portugal continental. El total de especies recolectadas fueron 16, de las cuales 9 ya eran previamente conocidas, mientras 7 son nuevas para la ciencia: dentro de estas, pertenecen: 1 al género *Pyrgulina*, 4 al género *Odostomia*, y 2 al género *Eulimella*. *Chrysallida stefanisi* (Jeffreys, 1869) es transferida a *Pyrgulina* y comparada con la nueva especie Además, 8 especies son nuevas citas para Josephine Seamount (1 *Parthenina*, 2 *Odostomia*, 1 *Ondina*, 1 *Eulimella* y 4 *Turbonilla*).

INTRODUCTION

The Pyramidellidae of the Eastern Atlantic have been studied in numerous works, although samplings from great depths are less than frequent. Among the oldest of those are reports by MONTEROSATO (1874, 1875), DAUTZENBERG

(1889), DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1896, 1897), LOCARD (1897); more recent studies were published by NOFRONI (1988), AARTSEN, GITTENBERGER & GOUD (1998) and PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a, b).

*Olerdola, 39-5°C, 08800 Vilanova i la Geltrú, Barcelona, Spain

** Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela, Parque Vista Alegre, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain

*** Eikstraat 13, 3920 Lommel, Belgium, Research Associate of the MMF, Funchal, Madeira and RBINS, Brussels, Belgium, <f.swinnen.lommel@telenet.be>

A seamount is a mountain rising from the ocean seafloor that does not reach to the water's surface (sea level), and thus is not an island, islet or cliff-rock. Seamounts are typically formed from extinct volcanoes that rise abruptly and are usually found rising from the seafloor more than 1,000 m in height (WESSEL, 2007).

The Josephine High Seas MPA is an area of approximately 19,370 km² surrounding Josephine Seamount (Fig. 1) and included in the OSPAR Network of Marine Protected Areas (MPA). It is located east of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, between Madeira and mainland Portugal, rising to about 170 m from the surface and is associated with several other seamounts. It is one of six OSPAR MPAs situated in an Area Beyond National Jurisdiction (AB-NJ). Josephine Seamount was the first seamount discovered as a direct result of oceanic explorations, and has been found to have high biodiversity, with high incidence of rare and previously unknown species as well as commercial fish species. The boundaries of the MPA were chosen to also include a portion of an adjacent unnamed seamount. <<http://www.mpatlas.org/mpa/sites/5497/>>

The present work is focused on the study of the Pyramidellidae found on Josephine Seamount by the expedition EMEPC/PEPC/LUSO/2012 made in the scope of the Portuguese Task Group for the Extension of the Continental Shelf between 20th August and 10th October, 2012, using the oceanographic vessel N.R.P. Almirante Gago Coutinho, and employing for collecting the ROV LUSO, with a suction sampler device.

The main goals of the EMEPC/PEPC/LUSO were the surveys near the seafloor to get geological and geophysical data of a series of pre-selected areas – for example, seamounts, fracture zones, hydrothermal vents, etc. The information and the rock samples obtained were then used to support the Portuguese Proposal to extend the outer limits of continental shelf. Along with the geological sampling, and when there was the opportunity to do so, the expedition also collected biological samples, in order to get as much information as

possible about the area. After the dives we analyzed the type of species, the habitats, the bottom morphology, etc. The Josephine dives in 2012 were one of these cases where the seamount and its surroundings were surveyed for geological information alongside with biological sampling and data.

The Pyramidellidae that are the object of the present work were collected on the 1st October, 2012, two samplings:

- Sample Code: L12D18B10S1; L12D18B14S2. Location: SW flank of the seamount, north of Josephine Seamount. Date of sample: 01 of october 2012. Lat/Long (WGS84): 37°00.983' N, 14° 14.802' W. Depth: 1336 m.

- Sample Code: L12D19B6S2, L12D19B4S1, L12D19B2S1. Location: Josephine Seamount, NW flank. Date of sample: 01 of october 2012. Lat/Long (WGS84): 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W. Depth: 769 m.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

From the small quantity of sedimentary material obtained, the shells were separated with a stereomicroscope, on the basis of their morphology. In the present work, the species included in the Pyramidellidae family are studied. Some hardly identifiable juveniles or fragments of shells belonging to the genera *Odostomia*, *Eulimella* and *Turbonilla* were also found.

The photographs of the shells were made at the Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación (CACTI) from the University of Vigo.

Abbreviations:

MUHNAC Museo Nacional de História Natural e da Ciência, Lisboa, Portugal
CFS collection of Frank Swinnen
s shell
juv juvenile
frag fragment
H total height
h height of the last whorl
D diameter
A height of the aperture

Figure 1. Geographic position of the Josephine Seamount (X).

Figura 1. Situación geográfica de la montaña submarina Josephine (X).

RESULTS

Family PYRAMIDELLIDAE Gray, 1840

Genus *Parthenina* Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883

Type species by original designation: *Turbo interstinctus* J. Adams, 1797 *sensu* MONTAGU, 1803.

Parthenina flexuosa (Monterosato, 1874 ex Jeffreys)

New material examined: 13 s + 7 juv + 1 frag., Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample code: L12D19B2S1, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (MUHNAC).

Distribution: Species known from deep water of the Mediterranean and European Atlantic, including Azores

and the Meteor seamount group; this is the first record at the Josephine Seamount.

Genus *Pyrgulina* A. Adams, 1863

Type species: *Chrysallida casta* A. Adams, 1861.

Pyrgulina scailleti n. sp. (Fig. 2A-B)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 2A-B) from sample L12D19B2S1, in MUHNAC/MB28-00561 and one paratype in CFS.

Type locality: Josephine Seamount, NW flank, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Roland Scaillet who has been studying the European Marine molluscs for 40 years now.

Description: Shell very small, fragile, globose (H/D = 1.6), whitish, not very shiny. Protoconch relatively large, type C, with a diameter of about 360 μm . Teleoconch with a low spire (h > 75% H), with about two convex whorls, the last one rounded in the periphery. Suture deep, with a wide shoulder below. Axial sculpture formed by numerous irregular ribs, little elevate, orthocline, about 24 on the last whorl, which are faded in the periphery, blending in the base with the growth lines. Spiral sculpture on the entire teleoconch, formed by shallow, unequally spaced grooves. Aperture relatively large (A = 44% H), suboval; columella opisthocline, arched, without a visible columellar tooth; umbilicus deep. Sharp lip.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.45 x 0.9 mm.

Remarks: *Chrysallida seamounti* Peñas & Rolán, 1999, described from deep water of Atlantis seamount, is smaller but more robust, with a truncated cone profile, the last whorl is angled in the periphery, the ribs are well marked, well prosocline, extended to the base, penetrating into the umbilicus; it has no spiral sculpture and the umbilicus is much wider and deeper.

Chrysallida boucheti Peñas & Rolán, 1999, described from deep water of the

Hyeres and Irving seamounts, has a smaller, plump shell, with the last whorl very angular at the periphery; the ribs are wide, well-marked, extended on the base to the umbilical area; it has a spiral microsculpture, only apparent under high magnification; the umbilical chink is narrow; the protoconch of the type C but tending to B is much smaller (diameter 266 μm).

Chrysallida pinguis Peñas & Rolán, 1998, described from the infralittoral of the African Atlantic, has a very robust shell with truncated-conical outline and stepped whorls; the ribs are high and thick, extending conspicuously on the base up to the aperture; it has spiral cords which are also evident and they overrun the ribs, lacks an umbilicus and the lip is thickened.

Pyrgulina stefanisi (Jeffreys, 1869) n. comb. has a shell with a similar profile, it also has an umbilicus and lacks a columellar tooth, but the sculpture is very different: the axial one is formed by about 16 very robust ribs, approximately as wide as their interspaces, extended to the base and penetrating into the umbilicus; the spiral sculpture is conspicuous, formed by equidistant spiral cords and not irregular grooves. The image in SEGERS, SWINNEN & DE PRINS (2009: plate 51, fig. 9) confirms our opinion.

Genus *Odostomia* Philippi, 1849

Type species: *Turbo plicatus* Montagu, 1803.

Odostomia cf. *striolata* Forbes & Hanley, 1850

New material examined: 1 juv, Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample code: L12D19B4S1, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (MUHNAC).

Figure 2. A, B. *Pyrgulina scailleti* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.45 mm, 769 m, Josephine Seamount, (MUHNAC); B: paratype, same locality. C-G. *Odostomia jesusabadi* n. sp. C: holotype, 2.11 mm in height, 769 mm, Josephine Seamount, (MUHNAC); D-F: paratypes, about 1 mm, same locality (MUHNAC); G: apex and protoconch. H-K. *Odostomia bapaulinoae* n. sp. H: holotype, 2.10 mm in height, 769 m, Josephine Seamount (MUHNAC); I-K: paratypes, about 1.20-1.30 mm, same locality (MUHNAC).

Figura 2. A, B. *Pyrgulina scailleti* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,45 mm, 769 m, Josephine Seamount, (MUHNAC); B: paratipo, misma localidad. C-G. *Odostomia jesusabadi* n. sp. C: holotipo, 2,11 mm de altura, 769 mm, Josephine Seamount, (MUHNAC); D-F: paratipos, aproximadamente 1 mm, misma localidad (MUHNAC); G: ápice y protoconcha. H-K. *Odostomia bapaulinoae* n. sp. H: holotipo, 2,10 mm de altura, 769 m, Josephine Seamount (MUHNAC); I-K: paratipos, aproximadamente 1,2-1,3 mm, misma localidad (MUHNAC).

Distribution: A common species in the infralittoral and circalittoral of the entire Atlantic, down to Ghana, including

Azores, Selvagens, Madeira, Canaries and Cape Verde. Its distribution area is extended to Josephine Seamount.

Odostomia jesusabadi n. sp. (Fig. 2C-G)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 2C) from sample L12D19B2S1, in MUHNAC/MB28-005063, 8 paratypes (Figs. 2E-F) in MUHNAC/MB28-005064 and 10 (juv) in CFS (Fig. 2D).

Other material: 24 juv more in MUHNAC.

Type locality: Josephine Seamount, NW flank, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m.

Etymology: The specific name of the present species is after Jesús Abad, from Vilanova i la Geltrú (Barcelona), a friend of the first author.

Description: Shell solid, conical, quite broad ($H/D = 1.75$), whitish in colour, not very shiny. Protoconch of type C tending to B, with a diameter of about 310 μm . Teleoconch of moderately high spire ($h = 64\%$ H) with three well convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, but not canaliculated. Axial sculpture formed by numerous growth lines, tightly set and looking like ribs, prosocline, very flexuous, prolonged to the umbilical area. Spiral sculpture formed by hardly distinct cordlets, unevenly distributed, more apparent below the suture. Aperture semicircular, peristome continuous, columella curved, opisthocline. Umbilicus deep; without a visible columellar tooth; outer lip thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.11 x 1.23 mm.

Remarks: Because of its quite conspicuous spiral and axial sculpture, this species

resembles the *Chrysallidini* group, but it is presently assigned to genus *Odostomia*. We do not know of any studied species of the European or African Atlantic comparable with this one. Only *Odostomia bapaulinoae* n. sp. (see below) has a certain resemblance, but the latter has a more conical profile, is narrower ($H/D = 2$), has slightly convex whorls, the sculpture is different, less conspicuous the axial and more evident the spiral; it has no umbilicus and has a columellar tooth, albeit not very noticeable.

Odostomia umbilicatissima Peñas & Rolán, 1999 has a shell proportionately wider, of pyramidal profile, with less convex whorls, the last one is very angular at the periphery, the suture is very deep, with a narrow but clear subsutural shelf lacking of spiral sculpture, the umbilicus is wider and deep, with sharp edges and the protoconch is globose of type B.

Odostomia bapaulinoae n. sp. (Fig. 2H-K)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 2H) from sample L12D19B4S1, in MUHNAC/MB28-005065 and 2 paratypes (Figs. 2I-K) in MUHNAC/MB28-005066.

Type locality: Josephine Seamount, NW flank, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Bárbara Quaresma Paulino, a young Portuguese Biologist who devoted her life to the Sea and who recently passed away.

Description: Shell small, solid, conical, whitish, not very shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 130 μm . Teleoconch with a low spire ($h > 65\%$ H), with about three slightly convex whorls, the last one rounded in the periphery. Suture shallow, not canaliculated. Axial sculpture

formed by growth lines, very evident at first sight, somewhat flexuous, very prosocline. Spiral sculpture in all the teleoconch formed by irregular, also evident cordlets. Aperture suboval, columella curved, opisthocline, with a narrow but deep umbilical fissure behind it; with a weak columellar tooth.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.10 x 1.16 mm.

Remarks: See comments under *Odostomia jesusabadi* n. sp.

Odostomia striolata Forbes & Hanley, 1850 has a shell with a similar profile, but has a protoconch of type B, the teleoconch whorls are almost flat, and it has as only evident sculpture a subsutural groove and the microsculpture, when present at all, is only visible under high magnification; it also has a more conspicuous columellar tooth.

Odostomia kuiperi Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1999, described from the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Azores, has a wider shell ($H/D = 1.75$ as compared to 2.2 in *Odostomia bapaulinoae*), it has a protoconch of type B, the teleoconch whorls are more convex, with a deeper suture, its growth lines are inconspicuous and slightly prosocline, and it has not conspicuous spiral sculpture.

Odostomia brandhorsti Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, described from the circalittoral of the Cape Verde archi-

pelago, and also cited from the infralittoral of São Tomé and Príncipe in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a), has a shell of similar profile, but it is tiny ($H < 1$ mm), the protoconch is characteristic with a cord like a carina, the growth lines are barely evident, rather orthocline, and the spiral sculpture is formed by weak furrows only appreciably under high magnification.

Odostomia striolata Forbes & Hanley, 1850 has a shell with a similar profile, but the protoconch is type B with helmet form, the microsculpture is spiral, when it is observable, is formed by fine striae and not by evident cordlets, their growth lines are prosocline and not flexuous, the aperture has not near an umbilicus or an umbilical fissure, and, above all, the main characteristic of this species is that it always has a weak subsutural groove that delimits a cord with the suture, which do not occurs in *O. bapaulinoae* n. sp. The subsutural sulcus typical of *O. striolata* can be seen very well in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a, figs. 234-240) while *O. bapaulinoae* has this area completely smooth.

Odostomia pseudoprona n. sp. (Fig. 3A-G)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 3D) from sample L12D19B4S1, in MUHNAC/MB28-005067 and 30 paratypes (Figs. 3C-E) in MUHNAC/MB28-005068) and 10 paratype in CFS.

Type locality: Josephine Seamount, NW flank, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m.

Etymology: The specific name alludes to the similarity with *Odostomia prona* Peñas & Rolán, 1999.

Description: Shell very small, fragile, conical tending to suboval, narrow ($H/D = 1.7$) white and glossy. Protoconch smooth, of type C tending to B, with a diameter of about 260 μm . Teleoconch of moderately high spire ($h > 70\%$ H), with almost three convex whorls, very rapid in growth, the last one oval in the periphery. Suture shallow, rather inclined, with a wide shoulder below it. No apparent axial sculpture, except for the growth lines, clearly marked, very prosocline; a spiral microsculpture can be seen at high magnification. Aperture relatively large ($A = 45\%$ H), suboval; columella thin, arched, without a visible columellar tooth. Not umbilicate. Outer lip acute.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.58 x 1.16 mm.

Remarks: *Odostomia bernardi* Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, described from the circalittoral of the Azores, has a shell more definitely oval, with a ration $H/D = 2$ in front to 1.7 in *O. pseudoprona* n. sp.; the profile of the whorls is almost stepped, the growth lines are not very noticeable, orthocline or very slightly prosocline; it lacks spiral microsculpture and has a columellar tooth.

Odostomia prona Peñas & Rolán, 1999, described from the deep water of Hyeres and Irving seamounts, has a wide, plump shell with a regular growth of the whorls, the last one

rounded on the periphery, the suture is not tilted, the aperture is higher ($A > 55\% H$); it lacks spiral microsculpture, and the protoconch is larger (about $300 \mu\text{m}$ diameter). Also, the protoconch of *O. prona* is not smooth, presenting a rough surface with small sinuous irregular lines in spiral sense (see Peñas & Rolán 1999, figs. 47-48) while in *O. pseudoprona* the protoconch is totally smooth.

Odostomia inestojeirae n. sp. (Fig. 4A-C)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 4A-C) from sample L12D19B4S1, in MUHNAC/MB28-005069, and one paratype in CFS.

Type locality: Josephine Seamount, NW flank, $36^{\circ}50.993' N$, $14^{\circ}18.689' W$, 769 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Inês Tojeira, Marine Biologist at the Portuguese Task Group for the Extension of the Continental Shelf, for her contribution to this study.

Description: Shell small, solid, smooth, conical wide ($H/D = 1.8$). White and glossy. Protoconch of type C, with a diameter of about $300 \mu\text{m}$. Teleoconch with a moderately high spire ($h = 70\% H$), with about three convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, with an apparent subsutural shoulder. No clear axial sculpture except for growth lines which are orthocone or very slightly prosocline. No spiral microsculpture. Aperture relatively large ($A = 45\% H$), columella slightly curved, opisthocline, somewhat thickened, with a prominent columellar tooth in the middle. Apertural edge not thickened. Umbilicus narrow and deep.

Dimensions of the holotype: $2.14 \times 1.23 \text{ mm}$.

Remarks: *Odostomia kuiperi* Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, described from the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Azores and cited in PEÑAS, ROLÁN & SWINNEN (2014) in deep water around the Canary Islands, has a shell that is much smaller with the same number of whorls, is less globose, lacks an umbilicus, the columellar tooth is pliciform, not prominent, and the protoconch is of type B.

Odostomia megerlei (Locard, 1886) is known from the circalittoral of the

Odostomia lesuroiti Peñas & Rolán, 1999, described from deep water of Irving and Atlantis seamounts, has a larger shell and also its protoconch is much larger ($340 \mu\text{m}$ diameter) and it is not smooth; the teleoconch whorls are more convex and have a regular growth, the last whorl is more rounded on the periphery; the growth lines are less prosocline; it lacks spiral microsculpture and the aperture is rather pyriform.

Mediterranean and European Atlantic to the Canary Islands. It has a more suboval shell profile, the suture is deeper, the growth lines are clearly prosocline, the columellar tooth is small and very internal, it lacks an umbilicus and the protoconch is type B with a diameter of $250 \mu\text{m}$.

Odostomia minormirabilis Peñas, Rolán & Swinnen, 2014, described from deep water of Madeira, has a fragile shell, is smaller with the same number of whorls, the growth lines are clearly prosocline, the columellar tooth is small, pliciform, internal; it has a narrow umbilical fissure but not a clear umbilicus.

Odostomia carrozzai van Aartsen, 1987 is characterized by having a protoconch proportionally very large, of type C tending to B, with a diameter of nearly $350 \mu\text{m}$, the profile of the shell tends to be suboval, with the last whorl oval at the periphery, the growth lines are prosocline, it has no umbilicus and the columellar tooth is weak and placed backward.

Odostomia hierroensis Peñas & Rolán, 1999 has a shell of similar profile, with the growth lines also orthocone, but has the same number of whorls with smaller dimensions (the holotype measures 1.4 mm), it lacks an umbilicus, the columel-

Figure 3. *Odostomia pseudoprana* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 2.58 mm in height, 769 m, Josephine Seamount (MUHNAC); C: paratype, 1.85 mm in height, same locality (MUHNAC); D, E: paratypes, 0.7, 0.8 mm, same locality (CFS); F: apex and protoconch of a paratype; G: apical view of the holotype.

Figura 3. Odostomia pseudoprana n. sp. A, B: *holotipo*, 2,58 mm de altura, 769 m, Josephine Seamount (MUHNAC); C: *paratipo*, 1,85 mm de altura, misma localidad (MUHNAC); D, E: *paratipos*, 0,7, 0,8 mm, misma localidad (CFS); F: *ápice y protoconcha* de un *paratipo*; G: *vista apical* del *holotipo*.

lar tooth is little prominent, very internally placed, and the protoconch is of type B in a helmet form.

Odostomia eulimoides Hanley, 1844 has a protoconch of type B, proportionally smaller, the shell is usually nar-

rower, with a fastest growth of the whorls, the last one is oval in the periphery, the growth lines are proscloine; it has no umbilicus and the columellar tooth is less prominent and more internal.

Odostomia megerlei (Locard, 1886) (Fig. 4D)

New material examined: 1 s, Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample: L12D1942S1, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (CFS).

Remarks: This species is known in the European Atlantic, Canaries and

Mediterranean. Its distribution area is enlarged to the Josephinae Seamount.

Genus *Ondina* De Folin, 1870

Type species: *Ondina semiornata* De Folin, 1872 (= *Rissoa warreni* Thompson, 1845)

Ondina mosti Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998 (Fig. 4E)

New material examined: 1 s, Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample: L12D19B4S1, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (MUHNAC).

Distribution: Described from deep water of Cape Verde Islands and recorded by PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a) for

Madeira. It is reported for the first time for Josephine Seamount at a depth of 769 m.

Genus *Eulimella* Forbes & MacAndrew, 1846

Type species: *Eulima macandrei* Forbes, 1844 (= *Eulimella scillae* (Scacchi, 1835))

Eulimella monicae n. sp. (Fig. 5A-C)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 5A-C) from sample L12D18B14S2 in MUHNAC/MB28-005073.

Type locality: SW flank of an unnamed seamount N. of Josephine Seamount, 37°00.983' N, 14°14.802' W, 1336 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Mónica Albuquerque, Portuguese Biologist at the Task Group who cooperated with the biological study.

Description: Shell small, solid, and regularly conical, white and glossy, with the lower half of the whorls semi-transparent. Protoconch of type B, 380 μ m in diameter, with a small inconspicuous nucleus, with a spiral shape. Teleoconch with a relatively high spire, with about six flat-convex whorls, with the convexity in their lower third, the last one rather angular at the periphery. Suture shallow. No axial sculpture except for orthocline growth lines,

fairly marked. Spiral microsculpture visible only under high magnification. Aperture relatively small ($A = 25\% H$), pyriform; columella curved, opisthocline, somewhat folded outwards, forming a narrow subsutural shelf. No visible tooth or columellar fold. Not umbilicate.

Dimensions of the holotype: 4.0 x 1.3 mm.

Remarks: *Eulimella similiminuta* Peñas & Rolán, 1997, described from deep waters

Figure 4. A-C. *Odostomia inestojeirae* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.14 mm, Josephine Seamount, 769 m (MUHNAC); B: paratype; C: protoconch of the paratype. D. *Odostomia megerlei* (Locard, 1886), 1.15 mm, Josephine Seamount, 769 m (MUHNAC). E. *Ondina mosti* Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, 2.26 mm.

Figura 4. A-C. *Odostomia inestojeirae* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,14 mm, Josephine Seamount, 769 m (MUHNAC); B: paratipo; C: protoconcha del paratipo. D. *Odostomia megerlei* (Locard, 1886), 1,15 mm, Josephine Seamount, 769 m (MUHNAC). E. *Ondina mosti* Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, 2,26 mm.

of Senegal, has a larger shell, the protoconch is very obtuse with the nucleus almost not visible, with an arch shape; the teleoconch whorls are flat, almost stepped, with a narrow subsutural shelf, the growth lines are rather prosocline; and it has a spiral groove located one-third below the suture.

E. unifasciata (Forbes, 1844), known in the European and African Atlantic deep waters, has a larger shell, with a flat-convex whorls and the convexity in the middle of the whorls; it has a characteristic brown band on the suture, a

weak columellar fold, and the nucleus of the protoconch arch shaped.

E. vanderlandi Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 2000, described from deep water of Cape Verde Islands, has a lower shell with the same number of whorls, is wider, the whorls are flat, the growth lines are very marked, opisthocline, looking like ribs.

E. fontanae Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 2000, described from deep water of the Azores, has a narrower shell (H/D = 3.6 against 3 in *E. monicae* n. sp.), the teleoconch whorls are flat, the

last one very angular at the periphery, it has a columellar fold.

E. neoattenuata Gaglini, 1992, known from deep water of the Mediterranean, European Atlantic, included the submarine Banks of the Meteor group, is white

with a clear yellow line in the lower part of the whorls; by transparence a spiral cordlet between sutures can be seen; also, it has flat-concave whorls and a columellar fold and the protoconch has a nucleus in spiral form.

Eulimella alexandrinoi n. sp. (Fig. 5D-I)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 5D-E) from sample L12D19B2S1, in MUHNAC/MB28-005074 and 2 paratypes (Figs. 5G-H) in MUHNAC/MB28-005075; 1 paratype (Fig. 5F) in CFS.

Type locality: Josephine Seamount, NW flank, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Paulo Alexandrino, biologist, recently passed away, who contributed to previous expedition to Selvagens Islands.

Description: Shell small, solid, sub cylindrical, white, shiny. Protoconch with a small nucleus of type B, with a diameter of about 240 μ m, with the nucleus in arch shape. Teleoconch with a low spire, with about five flat whorls, the last one slightly ovoid in the periphery. Suture deep, not canaliculated, with a narrow subsutural step. Growth lines scarcely marked, orthocone or slightly prosocline. No spiral microsculpture. Aperture pyriform, arched, opisthocline, without a tooth or a visible columellar fold. Lip not thick. Not umbilicate.

Dimensions of the holotype: 3.0 x 0.95 mm.

Remarks: *E. variabilis* De Folin, 1870, known from the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Atlantic West African coast,

has a larger shell, with a conical profile, the whorls are flat-convex, an internal spiral cordlet can be seen by transparency between sutures; the protoconch is proportionally larger, with the nucleus in spiral form, and there is a weak columellar fold.

E. kaasi Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, described from deep water of Cape Verde Islands, has a pupoid shell in its adapical part, with the protoconch very obtuse, with an unobscure nucleus, the whorls are flat-concave, the last one angled in the periphery and has spiral microsculpture.

E. acicula (Philippi, 1836) has a protoconch of type A and the spiral microsculpture is almost always evident.

Eulimella phaula Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896 (Fig. 5J-L)

New material examined: 1 s + 1 juv, Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample code: L12D198B, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (MUHNAC).

Distribution: Known from deep water of the Azores and of Irving and Hyères

seamounts, its range is here extended to include the Josephine Seamount.

Genus *Turbonilla* Risso, 1826

Type species: *Turbonilla costulata* Risso, 1826.

Turbonilla hamonvillei Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896

New material examined: 1 s + 1 frag, SW flank of the Seamount N of Josephine Seamount, sample code: L12D18B14S2, 37°00.983' N, 14°14.802' W, 1336 m (CFS).

Figure 5. A-C. *Eulimella monicae* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 4.0 mm in height, Josephine Seamount, 1336 m (MUHNAC); C: protoconch of the holotype. D-I. *Eulimella alexandrinoi* n. sp. D, E: holotype, 3.0 mm in height, 769 m (MUHNAC); F: paratype, 2.14 mm, same locality (CFS); G, H: paratypes, 2.07, 2.07 mm, same locality (MUHNAC); I: protoconch of the holotype. J-L. *Eulimella phaula* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. J, K: shell, 2.75 mm, same locality (MUHNAC); L: protoconch.

Figura 5. A-C. *Eulimella monicae* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 4,0 mm de altura, Josephine Seamount, 1336 m (MUHNAC); C: protoconcha del holotipo. D-I. *Eulimella alexandrinoi* n. sp. D, E: holotipo, 3,0 mm de altura, 769 m (MUHNAC); F: paratipo, 2,14 mm, misma localidad (CFS); G, H: paratipos, 2,07, 2,07 mm, misma localidad (MUHNAC); I: protoconcha del holotipo. J-L. *Eulimella phaula* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. J, K: concha, 2,75 mm, misma localidad (MUHNAC); L: protoconcha.

Distribution: This species is only known from deep waters of the Azores and of Atlantis seamount, here its

distribution is expanded to the examined material from Josephine seamount.

Turbonilla hoecki Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896

New material examined: 10 s + some juv and frag, Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample code: L12D19B2S1, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (CFS).

Distribution: Known from deep water of the Azores and from Atlantis, Irving

and Hyères seamounts, its distribution is expanded to the Josephine seamount.

Turbonilla mediocris Peñas & Rolán, 1999

New material examined: 4 s + 1 juv + 1 frag, Josephine Seamount, NW flank, sample code: L12D19B2S1, 36°50.993' N, 14°18.689' W, 769 m (CFS).

Distribution: Only known from deep water of the Meteor group of

seamounts, its distribution area is expanded to Josephine seamount.

Turbonilla micans Monterosato, 1875

New material examined: 1 s + 1 juv, SW flank of the N of Josephine Seamount, sample code: L12D18B14S2, 37°00.983' N, 14°14.802' W. 1336 m (CFS).

Distribution: Species known from deep water of the Mediterranean, Moroccan Atlantic and from Hyeres and

Atlantis seamounts, its distribution is expanded to include the Josephine seamount.

CONCLUSIONS

The study of the scarce material obtained from the Josephine Bank during the Expedition EMEPC/PEPC/Luso/2012, allowed us to describe 7 new species and also to register 9 new records for this area.

It is necessary to point out the coincidence of several species of Pyramidellidae found in this Bank with those described in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999b) in the "Seamount 2" expedition to the Atlantic submarine of the Meteor Group. The following species have been collected in both contexts: *Parthenina flexuosa*, *Eulimella phaula*, *Turbonilla hamonvillei*, *Turbonilla hoecki*, *Turbonilla mediocris* and *Turbonilla micans*.

It is rather surprising that a small quantity of material allowed us to find such a number of new species, but it

should not be forgotten that deep-sea bottoms have been poorly studied so far. It is also surprising that species which appear in other remote places, such as the Mediterranean, and other seamounts, are found in this study. This may be explained because pelagic larvae, carried by currents, can reach distant places.

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